

Exploring Factors Leading to an Effective Performance Appraisal System in the Telecom Sector of Afghanistan

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Abstract

The present study was designed to find out employees' perception of performance appraisal as well as exploring factors which could improve the appraisal system in the telecom sector of Afghanistan. Interpretivist philosophy, inductive approach, and phenomenological method of qualitative methodology were used. Data was collected through in-depth interviews with sixteen respondents from different departments of the selected telecom company through semi-structured interview questions. For analysis purpose, a thematic analysis was applied, and the conclusion was extracted from the transcribed data obtained through interviews. This study found out that employees' knowledge of the current performance appraisal was all about employees' assessment, motivation, and their output to the organization based on key performance indicators (KPIs) and objectives. Further, employees perceived performance appraisal as a periodic and continuous process through which the managers can differentiate among employees and can identify their strengths and weakness in the respective organization. This study concluded on the recommendation on how to bring effectiveness in performance appraisal system at the telecom sector, followed by some key recommendations for future research.

Keywords: Performance appraisal system, telecom sector, Afghanistan

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Introduction

Performance appraisal is although a controversial issue, but it is an integral part of every organization that is used to measure the employees' performance. Most of the national and international organizations are concentrating on this critical area of human resource management, as it helps the organizations to identify their employees' strengths and weaknesses, which can further assist the organization in improving the overall productivity of their employees. One of the challenges that most of the contemporary organizations of today are facing is to determine how to appraise an employee's performance effectively and to put this issue into practice. Performance appraisal is an effective approach through which productive employees can be recognized and differentiated. Subsequently, these deserving employees can be rewarded besides creating an image in employees' mind that the management values their efforts and hard work in the organization.

For performance appraisal, different definitions have been given: "Performance appraisal" is a process within the overall performance management process (Dowling, Welch & Schuler, 1999), it can be defined as the formal assessment and rating of individuals by their managers (Armstrong, 2012), and is also defined as "the evaluation of an individual's work performance in order to achieve at objective personnel decisions" (Robbins, Bergman, Stagg & Coulter, 2000). Generally, performance appraisal aims at recognizing the current skills' status of the workforce (Shaout & Yousif, 2014).

In order to evaluate employees' performance appraisal, various techniques exist (for more details see authors: Armentrout, 1986, Stronge, 1991, Sanchez and De La Torre, 1996, DeCenzo and Robbins, 1988, Arvey and Murphy, 1998, Jiang et al., 2001, Hroník, 2006, Chang and Hahn, 2006, Deb, 2006, Randhawa, 2007, Jafari et al., 2009, Khurana et al., 2010, Dvořáková, 2012, Aggarwal and Thakur, 2013, Kutllovci, 2014, Dagar, 2014).

Most of the authors mentioned above divide the appraisal methods of performance into the traditional method and the modern method. In creating and implementing an appraisal system, management must determine which system of performance appraisal will be used and then decide on the process of implementing the system.

In recent years, studies have demonstrated that the performance appraisal system entails biasedness and unfair practice by the managers in different organizations (Swanepoel, Botha, & Mangonyane, 2014), thereby making the performance appraisal as an ineffective system to enhance

efficiency and productivity of the employees. In some cases, employees perceive performance appraisal as a formality practice that is carried out by their managers in organizations (Ndung'u, 2012; Bitange, Kipchumba, & Magutu, 2010). Connected to this, the same perception of employees regarding their performance appraisals has been seen and reported in the telecom sector of Afghanistan, where performance appraisal is either taken for granted or as a formality practice carried out by the managers (Etisalat's corporate Human Resource Report, 2017). The report further identified that decisions pertaining to human resources such as promotion, demotion, reward, bonus and upgradation of employees are based on employees' performance, however, the final output of the performance appraisal is only shared with a specific department or unit instead of the concerned employees. Consequently, employees in the telecom sector organizations could be observed unenthusiastic and indifferent about their performance appraisals. This is an indication of the fact that the prevailing performance appraisal system in the telecom sector is ineffective, and it needs to be amended and refined.

Thus, in response to above mentioned issues, the present study was designed to provide answers to the following research questions;

- (RQ) 1:** What is the perception and knowledge of employees about the prevailing performance appraisal practices in the telecom sector of Afghanistan?
- (RQ) 2:** How the current performance appraisal system can further be improved in the telecom sector of Afghanistan?

In agreement with Ghauri (2012), it is argued that bringing refinement in the existing performance appraisal system in the telecom sector will not only help in changing the perception of employees towards performance appraisal system but will also help in enhancing the satisfaction and motivation level of employees in the telecom sector.

2. Literature Review

In organizations, performance appraisal systems are used to enhance employees' organizational commitment, their levels of job happiness, and job enthusiasm (Taylor et al., 2001). Hence, the performance appraisal system should be more productive. Otherwise, it will be a waste of time and organizational resources. According to Armstrong and Taylor (2014), an effective performance appraisal system boosts employees' motivation and productivity. For a performance appraisal system to be more effective and acceptable to the users, Elverfeldt (2005) identified four essential criterions. First, the performance appraisal should address the rating approaches and

rating techniques clearly. Second, the rating accuracy and bias in the existing system should be discussed. The third as a next step should cover performance feedback. Fourth, the influence of the training program should be analyzed, and the last part should be dedicated to employees' engagement into the system of performance appraisal. With regards to performance appraisal, Islam (2005) opined that before assessing organizational performance, it is better to evaluate and assess the performance of employees of that organization first. Employees, as well as managers, often question why organizations do employee performance appraisals. According to Lotich (2018) anyone who has ever been on the receiving end of a performance appraisal could argue why they perceive it to be ineffective and a complete waste of time. Employees often feel unjustly assessed, and managers often go through a forced annual process to comply with job expectations. This doesn't make it easy for either party.

A large number of managers, human resource professionals, human resource consultants and researchers are recommending companies to get rid of the performance appraisal systems. The main argument given by the researchers is that the system of performance appraisals itself is based on a few wrong assumptions and it fails to fulfill its basic purpose.

The major arguments against performance appraisal given in favor of abolishing the performance appraisals are:

The first and the foremost argument is the fact that discrepancies between the theory and its application. There is often disconnect between the theory and the practical implementation. Also, whether the performance appraisal boosts employees' motivation at the workplace or not, this question was addressed by the research of Jose (2011) in one of the Irish based companies that the researcher was employed with. The company was facing some problems related to performance appraisal and was not able to reach its goal and objectives for many years. Interestingly, both the managers and the employees in the same company were not interested in doing performance appraisals, believing that it is just wasting of time and considered a forced activity to do so. Data were collected using both qualitative (semi-structured interviews) and quantitative (closed-ended questions) methods from a sample of 45 respondents involving both department heads and staffs. The study concluded on the following two main reasons that the employees were not interested in their performance appraisal. First, the employees were unclear about the process as they had no ideas what the performance was all about. Second, employees had the perception that the process was ineffective as no action was taken by the management after reviewing performance appraisal. The study concluded

the following solutions to overcome this situation. First, the management needs to improve the communication barrier, make employees' mind clear about performance appraisal and its importance for the present and future plan and finally how it will help the organization reach its goals and objectives in the long run. This, in turn, will motivate the employees of the organization.

Performance appraisal is a vital tool in the organization to measure the target set by managers to employees. In addition to that, it is individuals' contribution and commitments towards organization goals and to find out weakness and strengths and as well as the opportunities for the future plan if it is done properly. It will further enhance employees' productivity. In alignment with this Armstrong (2006) and Daoanis (2012) argued that the performance appraisal should clearly define performance standards and regular discussion of the work process and developing an action plan as a consequence of appraisal should be done.

3. Methodology

Interpretivist philosophy, inductive approach was designed according to the nature of present. The nature of this research was exploratory and the research type of this study was "applied" since the focus was to find specific causes of the problem and its appropriate solutions. Qualitative studies that focus on phenomenological dimensions often propose interviews. Therefore, face-to-face interviews were conducted on an average time of 12 minutes with sixteen (16) concerned individuals from different departments of Etisalat Afghanistan as one of the telecom organizations. The main reason for choosing respondents from the Etisalat Afghanistan was that the customer complaints were increasing and its core employees were leaving periodically which had been causing its growth to slow down.

The sampling techniques for this research was purposive sampling method that involved identifying and choosing respondents who had expertise and experience with the phenomenon of the study and could speak openly about the subject matter.

Semi-Structured interviews were conducted to gather responses from the study participants. The interviews were held at the respective respondents' offices, and the questions asked during interviews were fully recorded, typed, and transcribed for analysis. Though, the interviews were recorded in Pashto, Dari, and English languages. However, an utmost care was taken to translate those responses into English language.

Table1: Respondents Profile Analysis Method

Employees’ Departments	Frequency	Percent
Employees from Marketing	5	31.25
Employees from Sales	3	18.75
Employees from Customer Care	8	50
Total	16	100

Source: Survey

Figure 1: Respondents Frequency

Source: Table 1

3.1 Analysis Method

The data was analyzed through cumulative themes analysis, the information from the respondents was fully typed, and the central and common texts among all the respondents’ answers were highlighted and analyzed. Finally, recommendations were made based on data interpretation and conclusion.

So the overall analysis process followed the following pattern as shown in figure 2.

Figure 2: Analysis process

Source: Authors Compilation

4. Analysis and interpretation

To find out the answers to the aforementioned two main research questions, a set of questions were further developed and asked. For analysis, one example as a common view is in place for each interview questions.

The following five interview questions (Int.Qs) were asked to find out the answer to the present study’s first research question.

Int.Q 1.1 What does performance appraisal mean to you?

Respondent: “Performance appraisal as the name suggest, it is just a method of evaluating performance your employees, performance

evaluation is always an ongoing process that you are getting info about your employees, researching about your employees, analyzing the data the info about your employees and making decision-based on that” [Marketing - VAS]

Int.Q 1.2 What are the objectives of performance appraisal?

Respondent: When the employees are appraised, we can differentiate the good and bad employees, so we can reward the good ones by promotions, bonuses or whatever reward is available for employees in the company and then we can coach and monitor the bad employees to know their faults and amend them in the upcoming months and year.” [Marketing- Product]

Int.Q 1.3 Does the performance appraisal system help to identify the strength and weakness of an employee?

Respondent: “Of course because it is a system by which they assess plenty of the KPIs is competencies levels by which they are setting the KPIs from the very beginning of the year, and then they are rating and then waiting for the same KPIs at the end of the year, so that is a very like transparent platform by which they can identify the strength and weakness of employees.” [Sales Support]

Int.Q 1.4 Do any changes arise after apprising the performance of an employee’s? If yes, How? If not, Why?

Respondent: If you do performance appraisal, you will get the feedback of your employees, you will get the necessary need or requirements of your employees, through the performance appraisal you can find many opportunities for the future plan.” [Sales]

Int.Q 1.5 When is the appropriate time for conducting employees’ performance appraisal?

Respondent: “In my view as I... you know dealing my employees, It should be quarterly based, the shorter the period, the more clear and effective the appraising will be, you know in a shorter period that performance of an employee is exactly reflected in appraisal against the objective you have set for the employee.” [CC-VIP].

The following table 2 shows the central themes extracted from the responses for each of the above mentioned questions.

Table 2

Codes	Int.Q 1.1	employee’s assessment
	Int.Q 1.2	good performer and low performer – promotion - goals, and objectives
	Int.Q 1.3	gap analysis - strength and weaknesses

Int.Q 1.4	employee's motivation - opportunity for future plan
Int.Q 1.5	periodic performance appraisal

Source: Responses from the interviews

Findings for RQ 1

To describe the finding from the research question (RQ1) and its related interview questions (IQs), the below Figure 2 was developed with regards to employees' knowledge about the performance appraisal.

Figure 3: Employees understating of PAS

Source: output generated from the interviews

The short description of each of the extracted themes is provided below:

Int.Q 1.1 Employee' Assessment

The finding indicates that most of the employees pointed out that the existing performance appraisal is used as a tool of employees' assessment and evaluation for their given tasks and objectives. Further, it provides information about employees, whether they are on the right track or not.

Int.Q 1.2.1 A good performer and weak performer

The finding from the above interview quotes declared that the prevailing performance appraisal is being used to identify different types of employees such as productive, weak, and the employees who like their comfort zone where nothing grows. As mentioned, each department had its own target and objective, so through performance appraisal, they came to know that whether the given target by the specific department was up to the mark or not.

Int.Q 1.2.2 Promotion

The finding reveals that the decision for the employees' promotion and demotion come through the performance appraisal process, the employees who have done an extraordinary job and performed well, they will be promoted to a more significant role where the management will increase their salary and other benefits.

Int.Q 1.2.3 Goal & Objectives

In response to the interview question, majority of employees replied that performance appraisal was all about goal and objectives which were set by their managers for their subordinates at the beginning of year and at the end of year and the employees were being evaluated for the tasks they accomplished.

Int.Q 1.3.1 Gap Analysis

Another significant finding by many respondents summarized that the performance appraisal process was the best way to identify gap in certain departments, in other word, this practice in organization helped manager to know and focused on the areas that needed improvements, so that the managers could decide on the employees who seemed less likely to be productive or unskilled and could not add value to specific unit or section. Therefore, the management could stop those routines through proper monitoring and coaching activities.

Int.Q 1.3.2 Strengths and weaknesses

Based on the finding of above Int.Q, it was also noted that employees' capability about particular task could be clearly identified, some employees might have strong desire to do an extraordinary job, in other words, some jobs might require technical skills, but all of the employees might not have those skills or potentiality. Therefore, through performance appraisal, the manager could set the right KPIs for their subordinates.

Int.Q 1.4.1 Employees' Motivation

Finding from the majority of the respondents signified that performance appraisal would enhance employees' motivation towards the given objectives if honest and transparent performance evaluation were done by the respective line managers in each department. Whenever the employees' outcomes were welcomed and rewarded, they would continue with the same effort for the years to come.

Int.Q 1.4.2 Opportunity for future Plan

Most of the respondents had clearly mentioned in their interviews that each department in the respective organization could decide for the future plans and the organization survival through performance appraisal. For instance, an organization can go for downsizing or right-sizing based on their employees' performance at the time of crisis and can decide on the employees' future employees' retention or dismissal.

Int.Q 1.5 Periodic Performance Appraisal

The finding from the interview data analysis exhibited that the current performance appraisal was not favorable for many employees in the Etisalat telecommunication company due to no continuous and regular feedbacks. The

current practice was done only twice year, once at the mid-year and the other at the end of the year, while the majority proposed monthly or quarterly performance appraisal to make sure themselves that they are on the right direction.

In order to answer the present study' second major research question which was "How the current performance appraisal system can further be improved in the telecom sector of Afghanistan"? A total of six interview questions (Int. Qs) were developed and asked. These Int. Qs along with the one interviewee's response as a sample are described as follows;

Int.Q 2.1 How Is Performance appraisal conducted in your organization?

Respondent: "It is your performance-based, whatever you are performing there are objectives and goals for you, your goals are set, your KPIs are there, your performance is the other side, just performance against your objectives those are compared, how you performed, these are numbers, so numbers are compared to numbers." [Marketing VAS]

Int.Q 2.1 Is the performance appraisal system helpful in reducing the Grievances of the employee?

Respondent: "Absolutely it decreases the complaints because after the performance appraisal is done the guy who worked well they will be promoted and they guys who have weak points they will be informed on their weaknesses and coached to be corrected." [Marketing -Product]

Int.Q 2.3 Does the current performance appraisal system measure employees' accomplishments accurately?

Respondent: "The current system, yeah, it is up to 70 % ok, because it is being judged by top management or supervisor, so accuracy should be there, transparency should be there even it will be better than someone from HR is there." [Sales]

Int.Q 2.4 What points should be considered in conducting performance appraisal?

Respondent: "There are a few points; we have to consider to make the employee's performance appraisal effective. 1st, we have to do fairly, 2nd, we have to involve two-three people to make sure it is going properly without any bias and 3rd after appraising the performance the feedback should be provided to the employees" [Sales -Support]

Int.Q 2.5 What type of performance appraisal process should be followed in your organization?

Respondent: "As the name suggests it is performance appraisal, so it should be all your performance 360-degree evaluation shall be there, your competencies, your abilities, the objectives and goals that expected from you

to be achieved all those things like 360-degree evaluation shall be there.” [CC-VIP]

Int.Q 2.6 Is there any action being taken after reviewing your performance or not?

Respondent: “Definitely in my department, we do take action if employees are not performing very well they are being transferred from their current location to locations where their performance might improve, and employees who have performed exceptionally well they get a very good bonus and they get certificates of appreciation from the departments as well.” [Marketing VAS]

The following table 3 depicts the themes extracted from each of the above Int.Qs.

Table 3

Codes	Int.Q 2.1	KPIs & Competency
	Int.Q 2.2	Complaints
	Int.Q 2.3	Transparency
	Int.Q 2.4	Communication - Monthly performance evaluation - Realistic goal setting - Timely feedback
	Int.Q 2.5	360 degree performance appraisal
	Int.Q 2.6	TNA - Rewards & Punishments

Source: Responses from the interviews

Findings for RQ 2

To portray the findings for the RQ 2 based on the related Int.Qs, the below Figure 3 was developed with the objectives of presenting main solution which was pointed out by the majority of respondents.

Figure 4

Source: Output generated from the interviews

The short description of each of the extracted themes from the above Int.Qs is described below:

Int.Q 2.1 Key performance indicators (KPIs) and competencies

The finding of the above question showed that the majority of Etisalat employees pointed out that one of the critical solutions to the improvement

of performance appraisal was standardization of the system based on the two components, i.e., employees KPIs and the competencies. These two components should match with each other; in other words, the managers and supervisor should set the KPIs or objectives based on the employees' capabilities.

Int.Q 2.2 Complaints and Problems

In response to the above Int. Q., many employees retorted that the performance appraisal should be conducted in a way to address the complaints or problems and forecast the solution for the employees and organization's future growth. For instance, the employees who are not performing well will be notified through performance appraisal about their pitfalls.

Int.Q 2.3 Transparency

Majority of the respondents proposed an honest and fair performance appraisal system for the Etisalat. One of the most common challenges and barriers in performance appraisal nowadays is biasness, which resultantly reduce employees' productivity. Thus, the performance appraisal should be conducted based on the employee's output rather based on the relationship being made between a manager and the subordinates.

Int.Q 2.4 Communication

Based on the respondents' feedback, the main problem was the communication between the employer and the employee in terms of performance appraisal, and that should be improved. KPIs or objectives should be clearly communicated to the employees at the beginning of the year. In other words, there should be a mutual agreement between the manager and the employees on pre-defined objectives to avoid future confusion.

Int.Q 2.4.1 Monthly Performance Evaluation

The finding indicated that majority of Etisalat's employees proposed monthly performance appraisal evaluation in which employees' performance could be measured easily and would be able to find out about their weaknesses in a given month. For example, if an employee does not meet the required target, he or she will be acknowledged by their line manager to fulfill the gap and pay close attention in the months ahead.

Int.Q 2.4.2 Realistic Goal Setting

In response to the Int. Q, some of the respondents pointed out a realistic goal setting as part of the performance appraisal process. To sum up their answers, they suggested achievable objectives and the managers should evaluate their subordinates based on the goals they set for them, not

against the target while in some department of Etisalat, the employees were not evaluated as per their objectives. Neither objectives were very clear, nor were they realistically assessed.

Int.Q 2.4.3 Timely Feedback

Finding showed that many respondents suggested timely feedback on employees' performance to make sure they were on the right track. Thus, if employees are performing well so that they will be motivated and will continue with the same effort. Conversely, if the employees are not up to the mark, they will be acknowledged to perform well in the future.

Int.Q 2.5 360 Degree Performance Appraisal

As another finding, majority of the respondents recommended 360-degree appraisal for improving performance appraisal system. In this method, many views are considered, and the employees are not only judged by their immediate manager but, it allows colleagues, peers, friends, stakeholders, and customers to come up with their ideas or opinions regarding individuals' performance.

Int.Q 2.6 TNA Program

The finding revealed that majority of the respondents thought that performance appraisal should point out specific training needs. In other words, that after conducting performance appraisal, the focus should be on employees' deficiencies and based on that the decision should be made on a customized training program.

Int.Q 2.6.1 Rewards and Punishments

In response to the above Int. Q., many respondents mentioned that performance appraisal should be followed up by specific actions. For instance, employees who have done the extraordinary job should go through a proper reward and incentive program, and in light of this, the manager could decide to promote them to the next higher position, but the employees who could not make it should be coached or punished to enhance their required skills.

4.1 Conclusion of RQ 1

To sum up the findings from research question one (RQ1), the majority of employees in Etisalat telecommunication company perceived performance appraisal system as a tools of measurement to evaluate and judge about employees output in specific unit or department in order to distinguish the outstanding and poor performers to be enlightened on the points where they really need improvement. Also the goals and objectives for employees are determined by the line managers in specific department through performance appraisal and then at the middle of year they go

through assessment to make sure that they are on the right track towards their KPIs and finally at the end of the year they are put under proper evaluation based on their achievements. Furthermore, they mentioned that through this platform, we could differentiate among employees and easily can decide for their promotion and incentive as well as future organizational plans. In addition to that, since the performance appraisal is a periodic and continuous process, so it helps us to identify employees' strength and weaknesses and go for existing gap analysis. Lastly, it has been stressed that performance appraisal will foster employees' motivation if this process is fair, transparent, and unbiased in the organization.

4.2 Conclusion of R Q2

To find out about research question two (RQ2), which was to indicate the significant solutions that can improve the performance appraisal system in the Etisalat company is making employees clear about their KPIs and competencies. Furthermore, the communication channel between employees and line managers should be improved, so that the employees will receive timely feedback on their performance and they will be notified for their weaknesses and the areas in which they need to pay close attention in the upcoming months. Moreover, the performance appraisal should be very transparent and based on justice. No relationship should be considered while appraising the employees by respective managers. In addition to that, the major solution in making performance appraisal system more effective happen when the managers do not wait for year-end appraisal, and they evaluate their subordinates on a monthly or quarterly basis to reach a very fruitful and breakthrough result.

In addition to the above solutions, 360-degree performance appraisal, training need assessment (TNA), reward, and punishment programs are the critical factors for making the performance appraisal system even more useful. The 360-degree performance appraisal is understating the employees from all angles or dimensions, in which the managers could know about their employees in details and use multiple channels of awareness about individuals' outcome in a given department. Furthermore, TNA is an essential part of performance appraisal in which the managers set the required training for their employees to enhance their skills and capabilities for the future challenge they may come across.

Last, but not least, each appraisal should be followed by reward and punishment program in which the high performers will be motivated and encouraged for their continuous effort, but the low or unsatisfactory result of employees should be acknowledged through proper monitoring or coaching activities.

5. Recommendations

The study proposes a set of following recommendations based on analysis and findings to improve further the performance appraisal system in Etisalat Afghanistan. First, the performance appraisal awareness session should be created in which all employees are informed, and their views and opinions should be heard regarding better practices of this process. Second, the performance appraisal criteria should be up-to-dated, and according to employees' current job description. In other words, realistic objectives and goal setting should be taken into consideration. Further, there should be a review of job analysis, job design, and work environment based on performance appraisal. Third, the managers in each department should be professional, fair and transparent while evaluating employees' performance. Also, trust and credibility should be built among employees and in line managers or supervisors. Fourth, timely and regular feedback should be provided to the employees to address their deficiencies and make them aware of their shortcomings in certain areas, so that they can work and improve them later. Moreover, a performance appraisal should be a continuous process rather than a one-time activity. Because the employees need to understand how they are performing on a daily and a monthly basis. Fifth, the managers should try to build up the right attitude in conducting performance appraisal. They must possess convincing power to help employees that this process happens smoothly. Sixth, the financial and non-financial incentive should be linked to employees' performance to motivate employees to perform better in the future. Moreover, competitive salary range should be introduced to keep the current staffs motivated. Besides, employees who have outstanding performance should be utilized as mentors or role model for other staff to perform better in the future. Seventh, two-way communication should be a part of the performance appraisal in which the employees express their thoughts and ideas openly. Also, long term and professional relationship should be improved between managers and their subordinates. However, personal contact and approach to managers should be avoided. Eighth, the 360-degree appraisal as a modern and professional process should be practiced by the line managers. As a matter of fact, many companies use results from the 360-degree performance appraisal programs not only for conventional application but also for succession planning, training, and professional development. Further, employees should be evaluated from all dimensions and his/her KPIs and competencies both should be considered. Ninth, training and development program should be part of each performance appraisal. Also, TNA should be developed based on employees' need and requirements.

6. Scope, Limitation and Direction for Future Research

This study found out that there are many ways to improve the application of performance appraisal system in Etisalat Afghanistan. The primary data was collected from the commercial division, which covered three major departments, such as customer care, sales, and marketing departments. Since this research was only carried out in Etisalat Afghanistan, so there is need of future research which will cover all other telecommunication companies in Afghanistan. Further research can also be conducted on the importance of MBO (Management by objective) in connection with performance appraisal which is not discussed in details in this study. Therefore, MBO is suggested in the next research as a performance appraisal tool in the telecom industry. In addition to that, future research should address the standard rating system, while addressing the performance appraisal issue, where employees should be ranked based on their output and productivity in the organization.

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